

PIFAGOR UCHLIGINI FRAKTALLANISHI

¹Ibragimov Husniddin Hikmatovich, ²Jovliyev Aziz Ismanqul o‘g‘li

^{1,2}Denov tadbirkorlik va pedagogika instituti, Surxondaryo, Denov

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Annotatsiya. To‘g‘ri burchakli uchburchak gipotenuzasida katetlari yordamida ajratilgan kesmalar bilan teng yonli uchburchak orasidagi bog‘lanishlar, teng yonli uchburchak va \mathbb{R}^n fazoda n o‘lchamli Pifagor g‘ishti orasidagi bog‘lanishlar ko‘rsatilgan. Hamda bu ishda teng yonli va to‘g‘ri burchakli uchburchaklar orasidagi fraktal bog‘lanishlar chizma hamda sxemalarda aks ettirilgan. Eyler g‘ishtining qirralari va diagonalini hosil qiluvchi qo‘shimcha $r \in Z$ parametrli tenglama keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: pifagor soni, Pifagor taxtasi, Pifagor g‘ishti, Eyler uchligii, Eyler g‘ishti, diagonal, to‘g‘ri burchakli uchburchak, teng yonli uchburchak, parametrli tenglama.

Agar butun musbat a , b va c sonlari uchun $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$ tenglik o‘rinli bo‘lsa, $(a, b; c)$ uchlikka Pifagor uchligi deyiladi.

1-teorema. Agar a , b va c Pifagor sonlari bo‘lsa, u holda ixtiyoriy n uchun quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} & (n-2)(c-a)^2 + (b - (n-2)(c-a))^2 + \\ & + \left(\frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{2}(c-a) + a - (n-2)b\right)^2 = \\ & = \left(\frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{2}(c-a) + c - (n-2)b\right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

tenglik o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

Quyida 1-teoremadan n ning ba‘zi qiymatlari uchun natijalar olamiz

$$n = 2 \text{ uchun, } b^2 + a^2 = c^2$$

$$n = 3 \text{ uchun, } (c-a)^2 + (a+b-c)^2 + (c-b)^2 = (2c-a-b)^2$$

$$n = 4 \text{ uchun, } (c-a)^2 + (c-a)^2 + (b+2a-2c)^2 + (3c-2a-2b)^2 = (4c-3a-2b)^2$$

$$n = 5 \text{ uchun, } (c-a)^2 + (c-a)^2 + (c-a)^2 + (b+3a-3c)^2 + (6c-5a-3b)^2 = (7c-6a-3b)^2 \text{ kabi natijalarga ega bo‘lamiz.}$$

2-teorema. Agar a , b va c Pifagor sonlari bo‘lsa, u holda ixtiyoriy n uchun quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} & (n-2)(c+a)^2 + (b + (n-2)(c+a))^2 + \\ & + \left(\frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{2}(c+a) - a + (n-2)b\right)^2 = \\ & = \left(\frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{2}(c+a) + c + (n-2)b\right)^2 \end{aligned}$$

tenglik o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

Endi 2-teoremadan n ning ba‘zi qiymatlari uchun natijalar yozamiz

$$n = 2 \text{ uchun, } b^2 + a^2 = c^2 \text{ Pifagor teoremasi.}$$

$$n = 3 \text{ uchun, } (c+a)^2 + (a+b+c)^2 + (c+b)^2 = (2c+a+b)^2$$

$$n = 4 \text{ uchun, } (c+a)^2 + (c+a)^2 + (b+2a+2c)^2 + (3c+2a+2b)^2 = (4c+3a+2b)^2$$

$$n = 5 \text{ uchun, } (c+a)^2 + (c+a)^2 + (c+a)^2 + (b+3a+3c)^2 + (3b+5a+6c)^2 = (7c+6a+3b)^2$$

Endi 2-teoremadan foydalanib (3,4;5) va (4,3;5) Pifagor uchliklari yordamida qurish mumkin bo‘lgan ikki seriya Pifagor g‘ishtlari qirralari hamda diagonalini 1- jadvalda keltiramiz [2-17 bet]:

P.G' \mathbb{R}^n	2-teorema yordamida qurilgan Pifagor g‘ishtlari (3,4;5)		2-teorema yordamida qurilgan Pifagor g‘ishtlari (4,3;5)	
	Qirralari	Diagonali	Qirralari	Diagonali
\mathbb{R}^3	(8,12,9)	17	(9,12,8)	17
\mathbb{R}^4	(8,8,20,29)	37	(9,9,21,29)	38
\mathbb{R}^5	(8,8,8,28,57)	65	(9,9,9,30,59)	68
\mathbb{R}^6	(8,8,8,8,36,93)	101	(9,9,9,9,39,98)	107
\mathbb{R}^7	(8,8,8,8,8,44,137)	145	(9,9,9,9,9,48,149)	155

1-jadval.

Xulosa.

Endi 2-teoremadan n ning ba’zi qiymatlari uchun:

$n = 2$ uchun, $b^2 + a^2 = c^2$ ($a, b; c$) - Pifagor uchligini,

$n = 3$ dan $(c + a)^2 + (a + b + c)^2 + (c + b)^2 = (2c + a + b)^2$

$(c + a, a + b + c, c + b; 2c + a + b)$ - Pifagor to‘rtligini,

$n = 4$ dan $(c + a)^2 + (c + a)^2 + (b + 2a + 2c)^2 + (3c + 2a + 2b)^2 = (4c + 3a + 2b)^2$

$(c + a, c + a, b + 2a + 2c, 3c + 2a + 2b; 4c + 3a + 2b)$ - Pifagor beshligini hamda

$(\underbrace{c - a, c - a, \dots, c - a}_{(n-3)ta}, b + (n - 2)(c + a),$

$\frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{2}(c + a) - a + (n - 2)b; \frac{(n-1)(n-2)}{2}(c + a) + c + (n - 2)b)$ - Pifagor n ligini

yo‘zishimiz mumkin.

Demak, bitta Pifagor uchligidan qirralari butun musbat

Pifagor n ligini, ya’ni n olchamli Pifagor gishtlatini qurish mumkin.

3-teorema. Agar ($a, b; c$) Pifagor uchligi bo‘lsa, u orqali bir juft Pifagor uchligi ($a_{11}, b_{11}; c_{11}$) va ($a_{12}, b_{12}; c_{12}$) ni ushbu:

$a_{11} = 2a + b + 2c, \quad b_{11} = a + 2b + 2c, \quad c_{11} = 2a + 2b + 3c$

$a_{12} = 2a - b + 2c, \quad b_{12} = a - 2b + 2c, \quad c_{12} = 2a - 2b + 3c$

qoida yordamida hosil qilish mumkin.

Buni quyidagicha 1-sxemada tasvirlaymiz (izoh: $\vec{+}$ ushbu belgi, o‘rniga qo‘yishda qo‘shishdan, $\vec{-}$ ushbu belgi o‘rniga qo‘yishda ayirishshdan kelib chiqqan ma’nosi o‘rnida):

$$(a, b; c) \xrightarrow{(2a \pm b + 2c, a \pm 2b + 2c, 2a \pm 2b + 3c)} \begin{cases} \vec{+}(a_{11}, b_{11}; c_{11}) \\ \vec{-}(a_{12}, b_{12}; c_{12}) \end{cases}$$

1-sxema.

Xuddi shuningdek, olingan ($a_{11}, b_{11}; c_{11}$) va ($a_{12}, b_{12}; c_{12}$) larni har biriga 3-teoremadan foydalanib:

$$\begin{cases} (a_{11}, b_{11}; c_{11}) \xrightarrow{(2a_{11} \pm b_{11} + 2c_{11}, a_{11} \pm 2b_{11} + 2c_{11}, 2a_{11} \pm 2b_{11} + 3c_{11})} \begin{cases} \vec{+}(a_{21}, b_{21}; c_{21}) \dots \\ \vec{-}(a_{22}, b_{22}; c_{22}) \dots \end{cases} \\ (a_{12}, b_{12}; c_{12}) \xrightarrow{(2a_{12} \pm b_{12} + 2c_{12}, a_{12} \pm 2b_{12} + 2c_{12}, 2a_{12} \pm 2b_{12} + 3c_{12})} \begin{cases} \vec{+}(a_{23}, b_{23}; c_{23}) \dots \\ \vec{-}(a_{24}, b_{24}; c_{24}) \dots \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

ga ega bo‘lamiz.

Agar $(a_{21}, b_{21}; c_{21}), (a_{22}, b_{22}; c_{22}), (a_{23}, b_{23}; c_{23})$ va $(a_{24}, b_{24}; c_{24})$ larni har biriga 3-teoremadan foydalanib:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (a_{21}, b_{21}; c_{21}) \xrightarrow{(2a_{21} \pm b_{21} + 2c_{21}, a_{21} \pm 2b_{21} + 2c_{21}, 2a_{21} \pm 2b_{21} + 3c_{21})} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \overrightarrow{+}(a_{31}, b_{31}; c_{31}) \dots \\ \overleftarrow{-}(a_{32}, b_{32}; c_{32}) \dots \end{array} \right. \\ (a_{22}, b_{22}; c_{22}) \xrightarrow{(2a_{22} \pm b_{22} + 2c_{22}, a_{22} \pm 2b_{22} + 2c_{22}, 2a_{22} \pm 2b_{22} + 3c_{22})} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \overrightarrow{+}(a_{33}, b_{33}; c_{33}) \dots \\ \overleftarrow{-}(a_{34}, b_{34}; c_{34}) \dots \end{array} \right. \\ (a_{23}, b_{23}; c_{23}) \xrightarrow{(2a_{23} \pm b_{23} + 2c_{23}, a_{23} \pm 2b_{23} + 2c_{23}, 2a_{23} \pm 2b_{23} + 3c_{23})} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \overrightarrow{+}(a_{35}, b_{35}; c_{35}) \dots \\ \overleftarrow{-}(a_{36}, b_{36}; c_{36}) \dots \end{array} \right. \\ (a_{24}, b_{24}; c_{24}) \xrightarrow{(2a_{24} \pm b_{24} + 2c_{24}, a_{24} \pm 2b_{24} + 2c_{24}, 2a_{24} \pm 2b_{24} + 3c_{24})} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \overrightarrow{+}(a_{37}, b_{37}; c_{37}) \dots \\ \overleftarrow{-}(a_{38}, b_{38}; c_{38}) \dots \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right.$$

ga ega bo‘lamiz.

Demak, ushbu fraktal jarayonni 3-teoremadan foydalanib cheksiz davom ettirish mumkinligi ko‘rinib qoldi.

Misol uchun $(3,4; 5)$ Pifagor uchligi yordamida uch bo‘g‘in fractal jarayonni 2-sxemada korsatamiz:

$$\begin{array}{l} (3,4; 5) \begin{array}{l} \nearrow \\ \searrow \end{array} \begin{array}{l} (20,21; 29) \begin{array}{l} \nearrow \\ \searrow \end{array} \begin{array}{l} (119,120; 169) \begin{array}{l} \nearrow \\ \searrow \end{array} \begin{array}{l} (696,697; 985) \dots \\ (456,217; 505) \dots \end{array} \\ (77,36; 85) \begin{array}{l} \nearrow \\ \searrow \end{array} \begin{array}{l} (360,319; 481) \dots \\ (288,175; 377) \dots \end{array} \end{array} \\ (12,5; 13) \begin{array}{l} \nearrow \\ \searrow \end{array} \begin{array}{l} (55,48; 73) \begin{array}{l} \nearrow \\ \searrow \end{array} \begin{array}{l} (284,257; 385) \dots \\ (228,145; 273) \dots \end{array} \\ (45,28; 53) \begin{array}{l} \nearrow \\ \searrow \end{array} \begin{array}{l} (224,207; 305) \dots \\ (168,95; 193) \dots \end{array} \end{array} \end{array}$$

2-sxema.

Endi quyida hajmi eng kichik Eyler g‘ishtini keltiramiz [1,3-15 bet].

$$\begin{cases} 44^2 + 117^2 = 125^2 \\ 117^2 + 240^2 = 267^2 \\ 240^2 + 44^2 = 244^2 \end{cases}$$

4-teorema. Agar $(a, b; c)$ Pifagor uchligi bo‘lsa, u holda ixtiyoriy $r \in \mathbb{Z}$ uchun
 $x = a[(br)^2 - c^2] \cdot \{(2b[(br)^2 - c^2(2r - 1)])^2 - (c[c^2 + (r^2 - 2r)b^2])^2\},$
 $y = b[(br)^2 - c^2(2r - 1)] \cdot \{(2a[(br)^2 - c^2])^2 - (c[c^2 + (r^2 - 2r)b^2])^2\},$
 $z = 4abc[(br)^2 - c^2] \cdot [(br)^2 - c^2(2r - 1)] \cdot [c^2 + (r^2 - 2r)b^2]$

noldan farqli x, y va z sonlari Eylar uchligi bo‘ladi.

Isbot. Teoremaning isboti quyidagi

$$x^2 + y^2 = d_{xy}^2$$

$$x^2 + z^2 = d_{xz}^2$$

$$y^2 + z^2 = d_{yz}^2$$

tengliklarni tekshirish orqali amalga oshiriladi.

Bunda, Eylar g‘ishtining yon yoqlarining diagonallari quyidagilar bo‘ladi:

$$d_{xy} = (c[c^2 + (r^2 - 2r)b^2])^3,$$

$$d_{xz} = a[(br)^2 - c^2] \cdot \{(2b[(br)^2 - c^2(2r - 1)])^2 + (c[c^2 + (r^2 - 2r)b^2])^2\},$$

$$d_{yz} = (b[(br)^2 - c^2(2r - 1)]) \cdot \{(2a[(br)^2 - c^2])^2 + (c[c^2 + (r^2 - 2r)b^2])^2\}.$$

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